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Molybdenum-catalysed asymmetric sulfoxidation with hydrogen peroxide and subsequent kinetic resolution, using an imidazolium-based dicarboxylate compound as chiral inductor

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Abstract. A catalytic system based on simple and economic molybdenum compounds and a straightforwardly prepared imidazolium-based dicarboxylate compound, as chirality inductor, was developed for the catalytic asymmetric oxidation of sulfides with hydrogen peroxide. High yields of chiral methyl phenyl sulfoxide and good enantioselectivities (up to 40 % ee) were achieved utilizing one equivalent of oxidant in one hour. By combination of the enantioselective sulfoxidation and the concomitant kinetic resolution an 83 % ee was obtained, an excellent enantioselectivity value for a molybdenum catalyst.

Keywords: Molybdenum; Asymmetric catalysis; Oxidation; Kinetic resolution

1. Introduction

Oxidation of organic sulfides is an useful and financially beneficial strategy for organic synthesis, since sulfoxides are key intermediates in the preparation of a range of chemically and biologically active compounds [1–6]. In particular, enantiopure sulfoxides has been shown to be efficient chiral auxiliary in several asymmetric transformations [7] and are also widely used in the pharmaceutical industry (for instance, (*S*)-omeprazol [8]). The main routes to obtain chiral sulfoxides are: (i) kinetic resolution of a sulfoxide racemic mixture, (ii) chemical modification of diastereochemically pure sulfoxide precursor, and (iii) enantioselective sulfoxidation of prochiral sulfides. Excluding the enzymatic processes, the latter represents the most challenging approach to chiral sulfoxides and both metal complexes [3,4,9] and metal-free systems [10] are known to be active catalysts in this process. Particularly, a number of transition metal complexes, mainly based on titanium [8,11–13], vanadium [14], manganese [15,16], and iron [17,18] have been shown to be useful catalysts. Molybdenum complexes as catalysts of enantioselective sulfoxidation have also been explored but, in general, they provided inferior results to those of the above-mentioned transition metal complexes [19–25].

The importance of enantiomerically pure sulfoxides encourages the search for other transition-metal-based catalytic systems. Good candidates are expected to be a metal complex easily accessible, simple, robust, environmentally safe, efficient, tunable, and compatible with a green oxidant as aqueous hydrogen peroxide. On the other hand, amino acid-based ligands offer a straightforward approach to generate suitable systems for applications in asymmetric catalysis [26–28]. Particularly, the interest in chiral imidazolium-based zwitterionic dicarboxylic acids has increased markedly in the last years due to their straightforward synthesis from amino acids [29] and their applications in the synthesis of chiral coordination polymers [30,31] and as precursors of chiral NHC-carbene ligands [32]. Following our recent research on Mo-catalysed sulfoxidations [33,34], we decided to explore the use of imidazolium-based zwitterionic dicarboxylic acids, HL^R, as chiral inductors in order to produce enantiomerically pure sulfoxides. Herein, we report the Mo-catalyzed asymmetric oxidation of prochiral sulfides using aqueous hydrogen peroxide in the presence of a chiral imidazolium-based dicarboxylic acid derived from *L*-valine, (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} [29], and [PPh₄]Br (Scheme 1).

[INSERT Scheme 1]

2. Experimental

See Supplementary Data.

3. Results and discussion

The Mo-catalyzed enantioselective oxidation of prochiral PhMeS using aqueous H₂O₂ as oxidant was selected as the model reaction. Reactions were carried out on the 1 mmol scale employing as catalyst precursor a solution of MoO₃ (2.5 % mmol) in aqueous hydrogen peroxide, prepared as described elsewhere and referred to in this work, for the purpose of simplicity, as [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] [35]. The catalyst was prepared *in situ* by mixing [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] with (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} and tetraphenylphosphonium bromide (see supplementary data). Table 1 reports selected results from the reactions carried out in a microreactor (1 mL of solvent) with a 1:1:0.025 ratio of PhMeS:oxidant:Mo-complex. Initially, several solvents were tested at 0 °C in order to evaluate their effect on the enantioselectivity of the process. The ionic liquid [C₄mim][PF₆] (C₄mim = 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium) was the first solvent to be evaluated (entry 1). In our previous work, we proved that [C₄mim][PF₆] is an optimal solvent for the selective sulfoxidation of sulfides when combined with aqueous H₂O₂ as oxidant and several simple Mo-complexes, including [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n], as catalyst [33]. However, despite the reaction was selective to the formation of PhMeSO, only a < 1 % of enantiomeric excess was achieved probably due to the low solubility of (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} in the [C₄mim][PF₆] solvent. Insignificant enantiomeric excesses were also obtained with other conventional solvents, such as toluene (entry 2), MeOH (entry 3), DMF (entry 4) or acetonitrile (entry 5). The low conversion and irrelevant enantioselectivity observed in toluene can presumably be attributed to the low solubility of the Mo-catalyst. In polar coordinating solvents, such as MeOH, DMF or acetonitrile, the almost null enantioselectivity can be explained by the solvent coordination to the metal centre that compete with the (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} coordination, limiting the formation of the Mo-catalyst responsible of the asymmetric process. From the different solvents evaluated, chlorinated solvent, such as Cl₂CH₂ (entry 6), 1,2-dichloroethane (entry 7) and Cl₃CH (entry 8) were showed to be the

most efficient, affording 32, 18 and 38 % enantiomeric excess, respectively. The use of these polar non-coordinating solvents facilitates the interaction of the precursor ligand HL^{iPr} with the metal centre rendering the process asymmetric. Following these results, Cl₃CH was selected as the reaction solvent for further improvements of the reaction conditions. Asymmetric sulfoxidation was found to be strongly dependent on the selected temperature. The increase of the temperature from 0 to 25 °C reduced the asymmetric induction, affording the chiral sulfoxide only in 10 % ee (entry 9). On the other hand, lowering the reaction temperature to -30 °C did not provide any benefit (entry 10) mainly due to a significant reduction of the conversion (37 %). Oxidation of PhMeS clearly proceeded via a metal catalyzed mechanism since negligible conversion was observed after one hour at 0 °C in the absence of molybdenum (entry 11). For the sake of comparison, *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide was also used as oxidant under the same conditions. The catalytic activity decreased notably with this oxidant (entry 12) and the reaction proceeds selectively to the sulfoxide as a racemic mixture, showing a non-asymmetric process. The [PPh₄]Br salt was a necessary additive to improve the activity of the catalyst for the asymmetric sulfoxidation. The phosphonium cation presumably behaves as counterion of the anionic oxidodiperoxidomolybdenum species, formed by the *in-situ* reaction between [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] and (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr}, helping to increase the solubility of the Mo-catalyst in the reaction medium. In all the reactions described above (entries 1-12), two equivalents of [PPh₄]Br respect to molybdenum was used as additive, giving the characteristic yellow color of the oxidodiperoxido-Mo(VI) species dissolved in the reaction mixture. Conversely, no coloration of Cl₃CH phase was observed when the reaction was done in the absence of [PPh₄]Br, indicating a poor transfer of the Mo-catalyst from the aqueous solution. In the latter case (entry 13), a significant worse conversion of the sulfide (38 %) than the reactions performed with the phosphonium salt was observed. Finally, an excess of the phosphonium salt (4 equivalents respect to Mo) was also showed to slightly improve the catalytic efficiency (entry 14), since an increase was observed both in the conversion of the sulfide (94 %) and in the enantioselectivity (40 %). Therefore, the [PPh₄]Br salt also seems to act as efficient phase transfer catalyst accelerating the reaction between reagents dissolved in the immiscible solvents H₂O (i.e. H₂O₂) and chloroform (i.e. organic sulfide). In order to gain information about the nature of the Mo-catalyst, the stoichiometric 2:1 reaction of [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] with the sodium salt of (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} was carried out. A yellow powder was isolated and the formulation

$\text{Na}\{[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2(\mu\text{-L}^{\text{iPr}})\}$ was proposed on the basis of experimental data and DFT calculations (see details in supplementary data). With the purpose of confirming the activity of this compound, it was tested as catalyst in the enantioselective sulfoxidation of PhMeS (entry 15, Table 1), under the same reaction conditions. The conversion (93 %) and ee (42 %) values obtained were similar to those of entry 14, thus confirming the Mo-catalyst nature.

The amount of H_2O_2 employed in all the experiments collected in Table 1 is one equivalent per substrate, because the use of two or more equivalents of the oxidant yielded the corresponding sulfone [33]. However, in order to analyze the possible augment of the ee yield by kinetic resolution, different oxidant:substrate ratios were employed under the optimized experimental conditions (entry 14, Table 1). Fig. 1 shows the results that confirm that an excess of the oxidant improve the ee of (*R*)-sulfoxide (at expense of the sulfoxide yield) because the (*S*)-sulfoxide was oxidized faster into sulfone than the (*R*)-enantiomer. The sulfoxide concentration follows a bell-shaped curve: after having reached a maximum at approximately oxidant:sulfide ratio of 1, the sulfoxide concentration finally drops off again when most of the substrate is consumed and the second oxidation step, to form sulfone at the expense of (*R*) and (*S*) sulfoxides, constitutes the main reaction. The sulfoxide (*R*)-PhMeSO was obtained in up to 83 % ee value, with a 1.6-fold excess of the oxidant.

[INSERT Figure 1]

Finally, the activity of the system was tested with other sulfide substrates (entries 1-8, Table 2) under the optimized experimental conditions described above (entry 14, Table 1). In general, enantioselectivities close to 40 % for the corresponding (*R*)-sulfoxide were found, with the exception of the sulfides Ph(HOCH₂CH₂)S and PhEtS with 21 % ee (entries 6 and 7) and benzothiophene with low conversion and negligible ee value (entry 8).

4. Conclusions

A simple process for the enantioselective Mo-catalyzed sulfoxidation with H_2O_2 , by using an imidazolium-based dicarboxylate derived from *L*-valine as chiral inductor, has been developed. The advantages of this system are: (i) better reaction times (1 h); (ii) commercial and cheap

molybdenum starting material, MoO₃; (iii) straightforward synthesis of (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} inductor, in comparison with the elaborated chiral ligands reported in the bibliography [20–22,24,25]. The performance of the system was comparable with the results reported in the bibliography for other related Mo-complexes (Table S1). Further studies are in progress in order to generalize this reaction with other chiral HL^R auxiliaries.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at:

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Scheme 1 Mo-catalyzed asymmetric oxidation of prochiral sulfides with H₂O₂ in the presence of [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n], (S,S)-HL^{iPr} and [PPh₄]Br.

Fig. 1 Sulfoxide and sulfone yields and *ee* of (*R*)-sulfoxide vs. oxidant:substrate ratio in the oxidation of PhMeS with H₂O₂. Catalyst: [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n]/(S,S)-HL^{iPr}/[PPh₄]Br, CH₃Cl, 0 °C, sulfide:Mo ratio of 100:2.5.

Table 1 Enantioselective oxidation of PhMeS with H₂O₂ to the (*R*)-sulfoxide with the system [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n]/(*S,S*)-HL^{iPr}/[PPh₄]Br.^a

Entry	Solvent	Conversion (%) ^b	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%) ^b	Selectivity to sulfone (%) ^b	Sulfoxide <i>ee</i> (%) ^c
1	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	100	100	0	≤ 2
2	Toluene	20	81	19	≤ 2
3	MeOH	97	97	3	≤ 2
4	DMF	54	95	5	≤ 2
5	CH ₃ CN	96	98	2	≤ 2
6	Cl ₂ CH ₂	93	95	5	32
7	1,2-Cl ₂ C ₂ H ₄	88	93	7	18
8	Cl ₃ CH	87	97	3	38
9 ^d	Cl ₃ CH	94	94	6	10
10 ^e	Cl ₃ CH	37	97	3	26
11 ^f	Cl ₃ CH	3	100	0	≤ 2
12 ^g	Cl ₃ CH	14	100	0	0
13 ^h	Cl ₃ CH	38	100	0	≤ 2
14 ⁱ	Cl ₃ CH	94	95	5	40
15 ^j	Cl ₃ CH	93	93	7	42

^a Reaction conditions: catalyst [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] 0.025 mmol, (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} 0.0125 mmol, [PPh₄]Br 0.0125, PhMeS 1.0 mmol, solvent 1.0 mL, oxidant: H₂O₂ (30 % aq), [oxidant]:[sulfide] ratio 1:1, 1h, T = 0 °C. ^b Determined by GC (50 μl of dodecane as the internal standard). ^c Determined by HPLC (see supplementary data). ^d T = 25 °C. ^e T = -30 °C. ^f Without Mo-catalyst. ^g Oxidant: *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide. ^h Without [PPh₄]Br. ⁱ With 0.05 mmol of [PPh₄]Br. ^j Na{[Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)]₂(μ-L^{iPr})} as catalyst (see supplementary data).

Table 2 Enantioselective oxidation of different sulfides with H₂O₂ with the system [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n]/(*S,S*)-HL^{iPr}/[PPh₄]Br.^a

Entry	Sulfide	Conversion (%) ^b	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%) ^b	Selectivity to sulfone (%) ^b	Sulfoxide (%) and configuration ^c	<i>ee</i> and
1	PhMeS	94	95	5	40 (<i>R</i>)	
2	(<i>p</i> -Me-C ₆ H ₄)MeS	90	97	3	34 (<i>R</i>)	
3	(<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄)MeS	90	93	7	36 (<i>R</i>)	
4	(<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄)MeS	91	92	8	38 (<i>R</i>)	
5	Ph(PhCH ₂)S	83	79	21	38 (<i>R</i>)	
6	Ph(HOCH ₂ CH ₂)S	80	33	0	21 (<i>S</i>)	
7	PhEtS	91	94	6	21 (<i>R</i>)	
8	Benzothiophene	40	100	0	1 (<i>S</i>)	

^a Reaction conditions: catalyst [MoO(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] 0.025 mmol, (*S,S*)-HL^{iPr} 0.0125 mmol, [PPh₄]Br 0.05 mmol, sulfide 1.0 mmol, solvent: Cl₃CH 1.0 mL, oxidant: H₂O₂ (30 % aq), oxidant:sulfide ratio 1:1, 1h, T = 0 °C. ^b Determined by GC (50 μl of dodecane as the internal standard). ^c Determined by HPLC (see supplementary data).